

2-METHYLBENZIMIDAZOLE AS ANALYTICAL REAGENT FOR SILVER

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2-Methylbenzimidazole has been used as an analytical reagent for the gravimetric estimation of silver. Influence of some of the cations has also been studied.

Feigl and Gleich (*Monatsh.*, 1928, 49, 385) have shown that well-defined salts of copper, zinc and cadmium are formed with benzimidazole. The reaction between cobalt and benzimidazole has been used as a test for cobalt (Yagoda, *Microchem.*, 1938, 24, 117). Preparation of some more copper and nickel complexes has also been reported by Ghosh (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 710). Benzotriazole, related to benzimidazole, and its 5-bromo derivative have been used by various workers (Remington and Meyer, Dissertation, Abst. No. 24, Ohio State Univ. Press, 1937; Tarasevich, *Vestnik*, Moscow Univ., 1946, 8, No. 10, 161; Cherg, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1038) as a reagent for gravimetric estimation of silver. Dutta (*this Journal*, 1956, 33, 389) has also reported benzimidazole as an analytical reagent for silver. It was therefore considered of interest to use 2-methylbenzimidazole as a specific reagent for silver. In the present work, an attempt has also been made to study the interference of copper, nickel, cobalt and magnesium in the precipitation of silver in the presence of ammoniacal ethylenediamine tetra-acetate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagent, 2-methylbenzimidazole, was prepared by refluxing a mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine and glacial acetic acid at the boiling temperature.

Stock solutions of AgNO₃ were prepared and estimated by titrating with standard thiocyanate solutions using ferric alum as indicator. The reagent being insoluble in water, a solution of the reagent in minimum volume of alcohol was used.

To 10 c.c. of AgNO₃ solution (containing 0.1183 g. of Ag), diluted with 30-40 c.c. of water, was added nearly 10 c.c. of ammonia solution (20 c.c. of liquor ammonia made up to 100 c.c.) to bring the *p*_H to ~10, indicated by the universal indicator paper. The solution was then heated to 60-70° on a water-bath for about 5 minutes. An excess of warm alcoholic solution of the reagent (20 c.c. of 1%) was added dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The mixture was then digested on a water-bath for about 10 minutes and the precipitate filtered through a previously weighed G₃ crucible. The precipitate was washed with warm water and dried to a constant weight at 120°.

Composition of the Silver Complex.—A known amount of the silver complex was taken in a weighed porcelain crucible and heated till the organic contents burnt away. When the contents became greyish white, the crucible was heated to red heat for half an hour, cooled and the contents weighed.

TABLE I

Wt. of complex (g.)	...	0.1792	0.1194	0.1074
Ag found (g.)	...	0.0808	0.0540	0.0482

The above results lead to the conclusion that the silver complex may be formulated as $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2)$.

The complex, when analysed, gave the following results. (Found: C, 40.01; H, 2.78; N, 11.57; Ag, 45.06. The proposed formula requires C, 40.20; H, 2.93; N, 11.72; Ag, 45.14%).

The influence of some of the cations in the estimation of silver by 2-methylbenzimidazole with or without the use of E.D.T.A. has also been studied. From Table II it appears that addition of ammoniacal E. D. T. A. solution prevents coprecipitation of foreign cations like Ni, Cu, etc. in the estimation of silver. Interference study was carried out as shown below.

Procedure.—To 10 c.c. of the silver solution a constant amount of each of the interfering cations was added. For each cation two sets of experiments were performed. In the first set the complex was precipitated after the addition of ammoniacal E.D.T.A. solution and in the other, it was precipitated without the addition of E.D.T.A. The method of precipitation was the same as described above. The p_{H} was maintained at 10 and generally 2 to 3 times the theoretical amount of E.D.T.A., required to complex the particular metal, was used to hold the metal in solution.

Ammoniacal E.D.T.A. solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount of E.D.T.A. in nearly 10 c.c. of ammonia solution (20 c.c. liquor ammonia in 100 c.c.). Table II shows the amounts of complex formed with and without the addition of E.D.T.A.

TABLE II

Ions added.	Ag taken.	Weight of complex		Ag as calc from the complex with EDTA.
		with EDTA.	without EDTA.	
Cu^{2+}	0.1177 g.	0.2605 g.	0.2983 g.	0.1177 g.
	"	0.2608	0.2986	0.1178
Ni^{2+}	0.0983	0.2190	0.2429	0.0986
	"	0.2186	0.2432	0.0985
Mg^{2+}	0.0983	0.2190	0.2290	0.0987
	"	0.2184	0.2286	0.0985
Co^{2+}	0.0963	0.2144	0.2424	0.0967
	"	0.2142	0.2420	0.0965

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